

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D2.3.1: New data about the valorized matrices characterization and high value products

DELIVERABLE D2.3.2: New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications

NB: D2.3.1 and D2.3.2 were merged

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	From M 8 to M 30
Periodic report date and version:	Ver_1
Deliverable # Responsible	UPO
RM2 Responsible	Arlorio

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Manager Data	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke manager Project	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.

Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Disseminati on Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
[number]	[name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products	R	PU	M14	18/04/2024
D2.2.1	On line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	Other (material)	PU	M18	25/10/2024
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	R	PU	M22	16/02/2025
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	R	PU	M28	30/09/2025
D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses	R	PU	M24	
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomasses	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization	Other (material)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-formulation (in collaboration with Companies)	Other (material)	PU	M32	
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32	

D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	R	PU	M32	29/09/2025
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A) INTRODUCTION

The partners involved in the activities related to the D2.3.1 and D2.3.2 (essentially related to the activities listed in Sub-Task 2.2.2) worked with the aim to characterize the materials/ingredients prepared at laboratory scale, as reported in M2.3.1. The principal aim of the material here described is related to the development of ingredients ready to formulate food supplements and cosmetic products, as well as to isolate bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical applications.

ROLE OF PARTNERS

The role of partners was distributed depending on i) the matrix and ii) the facilities availability, but particularly following the model process selected as best performing combined solutions useful to obtain sustainable new ingredients ready to be scaled-up and used in nutraceutical/cosmeceutical/food or pharmaceutical products.

The Deliverable (here considered as previously planned as unique Deliverable merging D2.3.1 and D2.3.2) reports the characterization of the products as outcomes of the processes.

As previously reported in D2.2.2, the four matrices selected were 1. Nervine foods 2. Rice by products 3. Fruit pomace and 4. Cow whey.

EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The overall work of described here was related to the chemical/functional characterization of the materials/ingredients produced.

Following, the main materials valorized and characterized (and ready to be used to scale up and formulate new products, as expected) are reported and described.

DSF-UPO

- **Apple pomace extract**

Fig. 1. Apple pomace after pre-processing (drying, milling)

Apple pomace extract was obtained through heat-assisted extraction (parameters: 80 °C, 40 min, 1:10 matrix : solvent ratio) and subsequent freeze-drying. The optimized parameters for the pilot production were optimized thanks to the use of advanced mathematical modelling (Random Forest algorithm, data not shown).

The extract showed a significant content of phloridzin (a target of the work depending on the bioactive properties of this compounds) when compared to the raw material, as well as a significantly high antioxidant activity. This product can be used both in food/nutraceutical area and cosmetic area.

More precisely, the apple pomace was pre-processed drying the material at 40 °C overnight and then grounding it using a bead mill, in order to obtain an homogeneous material (depending on the variability of the raw material, containing also grape seeds).

Apple pomace powder was then stored at -20°C until the analysis.

The moisture content of AP, before the drying process was 82.8 ± 0.4 % (fresh weight). The result obtained is in agreement with what has been reported in literature. Moreover, on the fresh raw material, the lipid quantification was obtained through a Soxhlet apparatus, leading to obtain 5.20 ± 1.16 % (w/w) of lipid. Has expected, this relative high value was strictly related to the presence of seeds in this by-product.

The proximate composition is reported in Table 1.

Proximate composition	Amount
Moisture % (d.w.)	12.3 ± 0.3
Ashes % (d.w.)	3.28 ± 0.03
Protein % (d.w.)	4.32 ± 0.30
TDF % (d.w.)	33.5 ± 3.3

IDF	23.9 ± 1.6
SDF	9.53 ± 0.21

Table 1. Proximate composition of apple pomace (AP): moisture content, ashes, protein and total dietary fiber (TDF) sum of insoluble dietary fiber (IDF) and soluble dietary fiber (SDF) content. Results are expressed as average ± standard deviation of three replicates.

Regarding the phenolic compound and the antioxidant activity, the analysis obtained from the material extracted using ethanol/water (70:30, v/v; solid/liquid ratio of 1:10) showed result in agreement with literature. Total phenolic content (TPC) was 2.48 ± 0.11 mg/g (d.w.) expressed as catechin equivalent, while antioxidant capacity (AC) measured with DPPH assay was 2.61 ± 0.01 mg/g (d.w.), expressed as Trolox equivalent. A preliminary extraction using only water as solvent showed result of 1.03 ± 0.07 mg/g for TPC and 2.05 ± 0.02 mg/g Trolox equivalent for AC (measured with DPPH test). This result can be influenced by the present of sugars which are co-extracted with water.

After the optimization of the phenolic's fraction extraction (experimental design not reported here) the extract richer in phlorizin presented an amount of $50.3 \mu\text{g/g}$, beside a significant content of hyperoside and rutin (evaluated as a sum of quercetin glycosides) with an amount of $95.2 \mu\text{g/g}$. It was also possible to identify and quantified cyanidin-3-o-galactoside ($4.93 \mu\text{g/g}$), apparently the only anthocyanin presents in the sample. All these characteristics allow to conclude that the produced extract is useful both for nutraceutical and cosmetic applications, as well as ready – after powderization – to be included in food supplements formulae.

▪ **Cocoa bean shells**

Cocoa bean shells, as reported in previous Deliverable, were processed using different methods from different Units of RM2. The following description is related to the processing selected by DSF-UPO.

More precisely, cocoa bean shells were i) directly enzymatically treated with Vyscozyme (1 % w/w), ii) pretreated with ultrasounds (15 minutes, 50 % amplitude, 50% sonication cycle) and iii) with a combination of both treatments. Fig. 2 shows the aspect of the different fiber- and polyphenols-rich materials obtained with different single or combined approaches.

Fig. 2. Cocoa bean shells fibers (before and after treatments)

Table 2 shows the different parameters measured in the same processed samples, particularly focusing on fiber fraction, polyphenolic fraction, antioxidant properties and sugar content.

	CBS	CBS+US	CBS+ENZ	CBS+US+ENZ
Total dietary fiber (%)	~66,5% (insolubile ~57,5%; solubile ~9,0%)	~48,4% (insolubile ~40,3%; solubile ~8,2%)	~50,5% (insolubile ~43,1%; solubile ~7,4%)	~49,4% (insolubile ~42,0%; solubile ~7,4%)
Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g)	12,98 ± 0,17	5,43 ± 0,25	5,72 ± 0,13	5,85 ± 0,03
DPPH (mg TE/g, frazione solubile)	13,91 ± 0,25	9,28 ± 0,27	9,56 ± 0,17	9,59 ± 0,17
FRAP (mg TE/g, frazione solubile)	17,02 ± 0,30	11,01 ± 0,01	11,12 ± 0,07	11,52 ± 0,66
DPPH QUENCHER (mg TE/g)	2,59 ± 0,06	5,70 ± 0,31	10,57 ± 0,09	10,95 ± 1,31
Total monomeric sugars (mg/g)	1,68 ± 0,03	1,29 ± 0,04	8,53 ± 0,85	9,19 ± 0,09

Table 2. Composition of the cocoa bean samples processed and ready to be used in model nutraceuticals/cosmetics

The data reported in the table 2 highlight significant differences between untreated CBS and those subjected to enzymatic and/or ultrasound treatment, as expected. First, the value of the total dietary fiber is significantly higher in the untreated sample (~66% w/w), consisting mainly of insoluble fiber. The treatments cause a marked reduction in fiber content: both the enzyme and

ultrasound (or their combination) lower the total fiber content to about 48–50%. This indicates a potential partial degradation of the fibrous fraction or solubilization into oligomers no longer detected as “fiber” in the analyses. In particular, insoluble fiber drastically decreases (from ~57% to ~40–43%), while soluble fiber remains low (~7–9%) in all cases, suggesting that most of the fiber reduction is due to the breakdown of the insoluble component. Previous preliminary studies confirmed that, despite the reduction of fiber fraction, the prebiotic properties increases (in terms of capacity to produce Short Chain Fatty Acids in vitro on fecal human microbiota, data not reported in this Deliverable). A specific research on this topic (prebiotic properties of cocoa bean husks extracts) was a collateral target of the GREEN-VAL Project (POC UPO Project – NODES), specifically dedicated to obtain new ingredients using subcritical water extraction.

The enzyme-driven treatments significantly affected the content of total phenolic compounds (TPC) and the associated antioxidant activity. The untreated CBS sample showed the highest extractable polyphenol content (≈ 13 mg GAE/g) and, consequently, the highest antioxidant capacity in soluble extracts (DPPH ≈ 13.9 mg TE/g; FRAP ≈ 17.0 mg TE/g). After the treatments, TPC decreased by more than half, stabilizing around 5.4–5.9 mg GAE/g. As a result, soluble antioxidant activity was also greatly reduced: in the CBS+ENZ, CBS+US, and CBS+US+ENZ samples, soluble DPPH and FRAP values drop down by ~30–40%, when compared to the control material. This decline indicates that a significant portion of antioxidant phenolic compounds was removed - or degraded - by the treatments (e.g., likely solubilized into the reaction medium and discarded together with the liquid not considered in these analyses).

Conversely, the antioxidant activity of the insoluble fraction (measured using the DPPH Quencher method) shows a marked increase following enzymatic treatments. In raw CBS, the antioxidant capacity of the solid is low (~ 2.6 mg TE/g), consistent with the prevalence of inert lignocellulosic fiber. However, after enzymatic treatment, the insoluble antioxidant activity rises to ~ 10.5 mg TE/g – four times higher than the control. A similar increase is also observed when combining ultrasound and enzymes (~ 10.9 mg TE/g). This suggests that enzymatic action (possibly aided by ultrasound) released or activated antioxidant compounds bound to the insoluble matrix (e.g., polyphenols linked to cell walls or roasting-derived melanoidins), making them more available to react with the DPPH radical. Ultrasound alone leads to a more moderate increase in insoluble antioxidant activity (~ 5.7 mg TE/g), lower than with enzymes but still double that of untreated CBS, indicating a partial exposure of additional antioxidant sites through physical disruption of cell walls.

Regarding monomeric sugars, untreated and ultrasonicated samples contain only small amounts (~ 1.3 – 1.7 mg/g). In contrast, enzymatic treatment causes a substantial release of simple sugars from fiber: in the CBS+ENZ sample about 8.5 mg/g of reducing sugars are detected, a

value that slightly increases (up to ~9.2 mg/g) when ultrasound is applied in combination. This result confirms that enzyme-driven depolymerization of the fiber (mainly hemicelluloses) releases monosaccharides, and that a pre-treatment with ultrasound can further (albeit slightly) enhance the yield of fermentable sugars.

In summary, the starting CBS matrix is rich in bioactive compounds, which, however, are largely lost from the solids after conventional aqueous treatments. Enzymatic treatment proves effective in reducing fiber content and releasing simple sugars, transforming the residue into a matrix potentially more digestible or suitable for fermentative purposes. On the other hand, such treatments reduce the polyphenols available in the solid, although part of the antioxidant activity remains in the insoluble fraction, likely due to compounds bound to fiber. The combined use of ultrasound and enzymes provides incremental benefits compared to enzymes alone: an additional increase in released sugars and insoluble antioxidant activity is observed. Ultimately, each process modification entails specific trade-offs in terms of the nutritional valorization of the residue: the choice will depend on whether the goal is to maximize the extraction of soluble bioactive compounds or to obtain a matrix enriched in modified fibers and useful sugars.

- **Blueberry pomace**

Blueberry pomace (BP), another material considered in RM2 project as raw matrix to be valorized, was treated with different carbohydrase and subsequent freeze-drying.

BP is rich in insoluble fiber and phenolics. Enzymatic hydrolysis with Extralyve® strongly reduced fiber and released soluble oligosaccharides. Untreated BP contained 569 mg/g insoluble dietary fiber (IDF) and only 6.82 mg/g total oligosaccharides. After 2 h treatment with Extralyve®, IDF decreased to 484 mg/g and total oligosaccharides raise to 59.8 mg/g. This represents nearly a tenfold increase compared to untreated BP.

Gluco-oligosaccharides (GlcOS) reached 18.3 mg/g, while fructooligosaccharides (FOS) reached 10.9 mg/g. Extralyve® also released hemicellulose-derived oligosaccharides: 5.5 mg/g XOS, 11.3 mg/g AOS, and 13.5 mg/g GOS. Such diversity of oligosaccharides is relevant for prebiotic functionality.

The treatment converted insoluble polysaccharides into a wide range of fermentable oligomers. At the same time, phenolic compounds were released, improving antioxidant activity. Untreated BP showed ABTS = 16.0 and FRAP = 36.4 mg TE/g.

Extralyve® (2h long treatment) improved these values to ABTS = 21.4 and FRAP = 50.9 mg TE/g.

This confirms a simultaneous liberation of oligosaccharides and phenolic antioxidants.

Compared with single enzymes, Extralyve® achieved the highest release efficiency.

The resulting matrix is oligosaccharide-rich, with reduced fiber and enhanced antioxidant potential. Overall, enzymatic treatment of BP with Extralyve® produced a bioactive ingredient with promising prebiotic and functional applications.

Fig. 3. Treated blueberry pomace

Tab. 3 shows the fiber and oligosaccharides fraction identified and quantified in the processed blueberry pomace.

Component	Untreated material	Xylanase 2h	Xylanase 4h	Xylanase 24h	Cellulase 2h	Cellulase 4h	Cellulase 24h	Extral yve® 2h	Extral yve® 4h	Extral yve® 24h
IDF	569±27	560±5	534±15	530±15	525±11	519±10	471±11	484±15	449±4	443±2
GlcOS	1.63±0.10	5.79±0.17	4.54±0.10	4.08±0.16	6.12±0.44	4.25±0.11	0.83±0.07	18.3±0.2	5.03±0.34	5.14±0.06
FOS	5.19±0.01	11.9±0.2	7.93±0.28	9.36±0.28	8.31±0.22	6.38±0.20	3.47±0.01	10.9±0.5	6.42±0.25	4.73±0.10
XOS	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	5.48±0.41	5.87±0.36	6.03±0.40
AOS	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	11.3±0.8	4.36±0.22	5.56±0.63
GOS	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	13.5±0.1	4.52±0.38	5.64±0.00
Total OS	6.82±0.11	17.6±0.4	12.5±0.2	13.4±0.4	14.4±0.2	10.6±0.3	4.30±0.08	59.8±1.1	26.2±0.1	27.1±1.0

Tab. 3 Oligosaccharides from blueberry pomace (fiber and oligosaccharides composition)

- **Peach and apricot kernel oils (cold pressing)**

Fig. 4. Apricot (sx) and peach (dx) kernel oils

Stones and kernels of “drupacee” fruits are an interesting source of oils. These material was considered in order to obtain with solvent-free extractions ingredients useful for application in cosmetical and food supplement area applications.

Apricot cold pressed kernel oil (AKO) and peach cold pressed kernel oil (PKO) were produced in collaboration with an Italian manufacturer (Fratelli Ruata S.p.A., Baldissero d’Alba, Italy) with an expeller-type press; these samples were obtained through a worm press (Archimede-like expeller pressing), avoiding any further refining process. They were kept in the refrigerator ($4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, Liebherr LKexv 3910) until their use in the experiments. Table 4 shows the fatty acid composition of cold pressed kernels oils considered in our study.

More abundant fatty acid (FA) in apricot kernel oil (AKO) and peach kernel oil (PKO). Results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of relative percentage. Different letters indicate statistical differences ($p < 0.05$) within samples from the same *Prunus* species.

All *Prunus* seed oils were rich in unsaturated fatty acids, which could exert positive health effects, as largely described in literature. The most prevalent in both AKO and PKO were oleic acid (C18:1, ω -9), followed by linoleic acid (C18:2, ω -6) and palmitic acid (C16:0).

Fatty Acid	AKO	PKO
Palmitic (C16:0)	5.06 \pm 0.09a	5.20 \pm 0.09b
Stearic (C18:0)	1.16 \pm 0.02b	1.42 \pm 0.01c
Σ Saturated (SFA)	6.22 \pm 0.11	6.62 \pm 0.10
Palmitoleic (C16:1)	-	-

Oleic (C18:1, ω -9)	64.7 \pm 0.1a	69.0 \pm 0.4a
Σ Monounsaturated (MUFA)	64.7 \pm 0.1	69.0 \pm 0.4
Linoleic (C18:2, ω -6)	25.8 \pm 0.1a	20.9 \pm 0.1c
Σ Polyunsaturated (PUFA)	25.8 \pm 0.1	20.9 \pm 0.1

Table. 4: Fatty acid composition (%) of Apricot Kernel Oil (AKO) and Peach Kernel Oil (PKO)

First, depending on the relative high concentration of mono- and polyunsaturated fatty acids, the thermal decomposition behavior and the stability of the oils were evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The outcomes obtained from TGA analysis are reported in Tab. 5.

Sample	T onset (°C)	T peak (°C)	Derivative weight/time (%/min)
AKO	326.5	433.2	21.7
PKO	320.0	435.5	23.3

Tab. 5. Thermal properties (T onset and T peak) of the oils in the temperature range 300–500 °C.

The decomposition of all the considered oils, attributable to pyrolysis characterized by the breaking of chemical bonds, occurs in one step: in fact, the TGA profiles presented a single thermal event in the temperature range 300–550 °C (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Thermogravimetric curves (TGA) and derivative thermogravimetric curves (DTG, insert) of apricot and peach kernel oils. A) results for apricot kernel oils, B) results for peach kernel oils. Non-commercial apricot kernel oil (NAKO), commercial apricot kernel oil (CAKO), commercial apricot kernel oil subjected to refining treatment (T-CAKO); non-commercial peach kernel oil (NPKO), commercial peach kernel oil (CAKO), commercial peach kernel oil subjected to refining treatment (T-CPKO).

The complete characterization of the oils (Volatile Organic Compounds, VOC's) was then obtained using GC-MS, comparing with commercial oils and commercial refined oil as reported in Tab. 6.

Volatile compound mg/kg	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i> L.			<i>Prunus persica</i> L.		
	NAKO	CAKO	T-CAKO	NPKO	CPKO	T-CPKO
Saturated aldehydes						
Propanal	0.007 ± 0.001 ^b	0.037 ± 0.004 ^b	0.502 ± 0.115 ^a	0.018 ± 0.002 ^c	0.129 ± 0.012 ^b	0.166 ± 0.001 ^a
Pentanal	nd	0.053 ± 0.003 ^b	3.742 ± 0.538 ^a	-	0.731 ± 0.047 ^b	3.344 ± 0.118
Nonanal	1.527 ± 0.263 ^b	0.275 ± 0.001 ^c	3.679 ± 0.089 ^a	0.532 ± 0.056 ^b	0.547 ± 0.068 ^b	5.435 ± 0.395 ^a
Unsaturated aldehydes						
Acrolein (2-propenal)	nd	0.005 ± 0.001 ^b	0.358 ± 0.059 ^a	nd	0.017 ± 0.001 ^b	0.097 ± 0.003 ^a
(E)-2-Hexenal	nd	nd	0.140 ± 0.019	nd	nd	0.027 ± 0.001
Aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes						
Benzaldehyde	5.953 ± 0.154 ^a	0.760 ± 0.032 ^b	0.013 ± 0.001 ^c	16.370 ± 0.905 ^a	0.011 ± 0.001 ^b	0.010 ± 0.001 ^b
Vanillin	0.002 ± 0.001 ^b	0.013 ± 0.002 ^a	nd	0.231 ± 0.001	nd	nd
(E)-Cinnamaldehyde	nd	nd	nd	0.398 ± 0.001	nd	±
Furfural	0.006 ± 0.002 ^a	0.026 ± 0.001 ^b	nd	1.326 ± 0.018 ^a	0.004 ± 0.001 ^b	nd
Terpenes						
α-Pinene	0.087 ± 0.017 ^b	0.614 ± 0.011 ^a	0.013 ± 0.001 ^c	0.017 ± 0.002 ^a	nd	0.010 ± 0.001 ^b
d-Limonene	0.347 ± 0.011 ^b	7.471 ± 0.128 ^a	0.440 ± 0.055 ^b	0.014 ± 0.002 ^c	1.885 ± 0.021 ^a	0.143 ± 0.009 ^b
(E)-4,8-Dimethyl-1,3,7-nonatriene	0.288 ± 0.012 ^b	8.467 ± 0.285 ^a	nd	0.004 ± 0.001	nd	nd
Linalool	0.058 ± 0.008 ^b	2.474 ± 0.012 ^a	nd	0.007 ± 0.001 ^b	0.053 ± 0.007 ^a	nd
Alcohols						
Benzyl alcohol	1.983 ± 0.132 ^a	0.603 ± 0.024 ^b	nd	1.412 ± 0.051 ^a	0.019 ± 0.002 ^b	nd
Furfuryl alcohol	0.010 ± 0.002 ^b	0.097 ± 0.008 ^a	nd	0.072 ± 0.008	nd	nd

Tab. 6. Volatile organic compounds of oils samples (NKAO and NPKO: cold pressed oils from Apricot and Peach; CAKO and CPKO: commercial oils from Apricot and Peach; T-CAKO and TCPKO: commercial refined oils from Apricot and Peach).

Moreover, in order to compare the volatile profile of the cold pressed oils, a HS-GC-IMS analysis was performed.

More precisely, 2D fingerprints obtained by HS-GC-IMS, a rapid method useful to fingerprint food samples, permitted to compare at qualitative level the VOCs profiles in cold-pressed oils identifying some key flavour compounds, using Kovats indexes.

Fig. 6. Comparison among the VOC's profiles of AKO and PKO using HS-GC-IMS.

POLITO

The activities described in this report were carried out in the framework of Project RM2, Sub-Task 2.2.2, which aims to isolate high-value ingredients and compounds from waste matrices, with the objective of obtaining up-cycled ingredients for applications in the food, nutraceutical, and cosmetic sectors. This task builds on the results achieved in Sub-Task 2.2.1, moving from laboratory-scale extractions toward pilot-scale processes in order to complete characterization and assess the feasibility of scaling up the most promising technologies. In particular, the valorization of apple pomace and berry by-products has been considered for the recovery of polyphenols and pigments such as phloretin and anthocyanins.

During the last reporting period, different pre-treatments and extraction methods were applied to improve the recovery of total polyphenols from apple pomace. The activities focused on thermal-stirred extraction (TSE), ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE), and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), all performed using water as the extraction solvent. A kinetic study was carried out to determine the optimal extraction conditions, including solid-to-solvent ratio, temperature, extraction time, and applied power. These optimal parameters were then tested at pilot scale, and their environmental impact was evaluated through life cycle assessment. Among the investigated methods, microwave-assisted extraction proved to be the most effective, providing the highest yields while also showing favorable environmental performance.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction also gave promising results, and for this reason, it was considered for scale-up.

In the ultrasound trials, a fixed frequency of 20 kHz was applied at constant temperature (60 °C), with a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:30 and an extraction time of five minutes. Scale-up experiments were conducted stepwise, moving from 50 mL to 500 mL, 1000 mL, and finally 5000 mL. The first three volumes were processed using the Sonics Materials VC 750 Ultrasonic Processor, equipped with different probes according to the working volume, while the 5 L trial was carried out with the Hielscher UIP1000hdT-230 device (Fig.1).

Figure 7. Apple pomace US processing (Hielscher UIP1000hdT-230)

Total polyphenol content was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method, and all experiments were performed in triplicate and statistically analyzed with one-way ANOVA and

Tukey test (Fig.

Tab. 7. Total polyphenol content (mg GAE/g dry basis) obtained at different extraction volumes (50, 500, 1000, and 5000 mL). Data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). Different letters above the bars indicate statistically significant differences among treatments at the 95% confidence level (one-way ANOVA, Tukey test).

The results showed that the polyphenol recovery was comparable across the extractions at 50, 500, and 1000 mL, whereas a significant decrease in polyphenol concentration was observed at the 5 L scale. This reduction can likely be attributed to several factors. Beyond the lack of agitation and the limited penetration of ultrasonic waves at larger volumes, the dissipation of acoustic energy plays a crucial role: as the working volume increases, the ultrasonic energy is distributed across a larger mass, reducing the intensity of cavitation in certain regions. Moreover, non-uniform heating at higher volumes can generate localized hot or cold spots; in hot spots, thermal degradation of polyphenols may occur, while in colder regions the extraction kinetics may be reduced. Another aspect concerns the effective surface-to-volume ratio, as particles in suspension may sediment without stirring, thereby reducing solvent accessibility. In addition, the propagation of cavitation is less efficient in larger volumes, with weaker acoustic fields away from the probe tip.

Future work will therefore focus on addressing these limitations. New configurations with improved mixing and energy distribution will be tested to enhance the homogeneity of the process at pilot scale. Adjustments in extraction time and energy input will also be explored to minimize degradation phenomena while maximizing yield. Alternative ultrasound frequencies or multi-probe systems may be considered to improve cavitation distribution in large volumes. In parallel, coupling ultrasound with mild mechanical agitation or flow-through systems could provide more reproducible and scalable results. These efforts will contribute to the optimization of the process, ensuring that the promising results obtained at laboratory scale can be translated effectively into pilot-scale production.

Final considerations and perspectives

The activity here described was primarily directed to characterize the material upcycled and valorized (or extracted/processed) using “green” methods, as well as to complete the description of the best performing material to be selected for the formulation of “final model products” within the pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic or fine chemical applications. These products were obtained – also in close collaboration with some Companies interested to develop new processes and new products, as described in the Project - applying the best performed methods/combined processes selected after the comparison of 10 processes (as

reported in D2.2.2).

The main material characterized (source of bioactive ingredients) were:

- Fiber from cocoa bean husks
- Extract rich in polyphenols and caffeine/theobromine from cocoa bean husks
- Bioactive polyphenols from apple pomace
- Bioactive polyphenols and pigments from blueberry pomace
- Oils from fruit kernels

More materials characterized in RM2 project (more particularly rice husks, soy, cow whey and biomass from *Elodea nuttallii*) are described in D2.4.2.